

A new dietary therapy for chronic renal failure: Intestinal dialysis technology

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The uremic syndrome

Chronic renal failure is associated with development of the uremic syndrome which is the signs and symptoms resulting from the retention of nitrogenous waste products, imbalance in the body content and distribution of water and electrolytes, and an inadequate production of renal hormones.

The uremic syndrome

The most prominent features of the uremic syndrome (nausea, anorexia, vomiting and fatigue) result from nitrogen retention with increase in plasma concentration of the products of protein metabolism especially urea.

Relevant urea Metabolism

Ingested proteins are degraded into amino acids and their metabolism by the liver yield nitrogen, mainly in the form of urea.

Principles of dietary interventions in chronic renal failure

Several products of protein metabolism have been identified, with urea being quantitatively the most important. Urea represents 80% or more of the total nitrogen excreted into the urine in patients with CRF maintained on diets containing 40 g or more of protein.

Urea enterohepatic cycle

Approximately 25-40 % of the manufactured urea are recycled through the gastrointestinal tract and excreted fecally. This extra-renal excretion of urea remains constant at less than 3 g daily even in uremia despite the marked increases in blood urea.

What if we can increase this extra-renal excretion ?

Urea enterohepatic cycle

What if we can increase this extra renal excretion ?

Peritoneal dialysis actually acts by shifting the urinary excretion of urea to the peritoneal excretion with use of intraperitoneal dialysis fluids.

Intestinal dialysis

What if we can use a dietary material to increase this extra renal excretion and shift the urinary excretion of urea to the intestinal excretion.

Can we call this process “Intestinal dialysis technology”?

Management of non-terminal chronic renal failure

is largely directed at compensating the diminished renal functions conservatively through dietary and pharmacologic measures which include protein and phosphorus restriction, calorie and water soluble vitamins supplementation, phosphate binders, and correction of other abnormalities that may be associated with CRF such as fluid and salt retention, hypocalcaemia, hyperkalemia and hypertension

Principles of dietary interventions in chronic renal failure

The dietary interventions in CRF are directed at diminishing the accumulation of the products of nitrogen metabolism which are responsible for many of the symptoms and disturbances of uremia, and thus preventing the development of the uremic symptoms complications.

Principles of dietary interventions in chronic renal failure

The most essential strategy directed toward diminishing the accumulation of the products of nitrogen metabolism in CRF is dietary protein restriction and this can be achieved safely with avoiding consequences of protein deficiency through the provision of low quantity of high quality protein diet.

Principles of dietary interventions in chronic renal failure

High biologic value proteins reduce the accumulation of nitrogenous waste products and acid load for renal excretion and also helps in maintaining a positive nitrogen balance. Egg protein has the highest biologic value(1 large egg contains 6 g protein).

Principles of dietary interventions in chronic renal failure

It's very difficult and not really practical to limit the intake of proteins only to the high biologic value egg protein, and preferably 50% of the protein intake should be provided as egg, and 50% provided with the intake of vegetables, rice, and bread. Thus, avoiding restriction of caloric intake which may lead to negative nitrogen balance, muscle wasting and growth failure in case of children.

The rational for protein restriction in CRF

Protein restriction decreases endogenous protein catabolism and the accumulation of nitrogenous waste products, also reduces the phosphorus load and thus may prevent the onset of secondary hyperparathyroidism and renal osteodystrophy.

The rational for protein restriction in CRF

Protein restriction also reduces the intake of potential hydrogen ion, because every 10 g of protein provides 7 meq of hydrogen ion in the form of sulfated amino-acids
.Therefore, protein restriction helps to ameliorate acidosis.

Principles of dietary interventions in chronic renal failure

The second necessary strategy directed toward diminishing the accumulation of the products of nitrogen metabolism is the adequate intake of Adequate intake of carbohydrate and fats for their protein sparing effect which decreases endogenous protein catabolism and the production of urea.

Principles of dietary interventions in chronic renal failure

Fats are less effective than carbohydrates in minimizing protein catabolism, but they are given to provide essential fatty acids and to enhance the palatability of the diet.

Principles of dietary interventions in chronic renal failure

Dietary restrictions of sodium and potassium depend on the presence of oliguria, edema, hypertension, and hyperkalemia.

Pharmacologic management of non-terminal CRF

Pharmacologic measures used to prevent or correct abnormalities which are expected to appear during the course of CRF including anemia, iron and vitamins deficiencies, hypocalcaemia, hyperphosphatemia, hypertension, acidosis, growth retardation, renal osteodysrtrophy.

What make intestinal (dietary) dialysis possible?

With appropriate dietary and pharmacologic management, patients with non-terminal CRF can be maintained surprisingly well and the transition from non-terminal CRF to ESRF represents a small decrement of renal function resulting in a large physiologic hurdle for the patient.

What make intestinal (dietary) dialysis possible?

Dietary and pharmacologic measures are only successful in non-terminal chronic renal failure (CRF) patients.

The addition to these effective traditional measures, a dietary agent that enhances extra-renal fecal nitrogen excretion can possibly bridge this gap resulting from this small decrement of renal function and obviating the need for dialysis for some period of time.

Urea lowering effect of dietary fibers including acacia gum

As early as 1980, Yatzidis et al showed that dietary fiber (locust bean gum) supplementation of CRF patients on low-protein diet reduced serum urea and creatinine by 11-23% over 5 days of intake. Improvement of clinical symptoms was observed during this period and deterioration was observed when supplementation was stopped.

Urea lowering effect of dietary fibers including acacia gum

In 1984, Rampton et al reported that six and 8 weeks of ispaghula and arabinogalactan reduced mean plasma urea level in uremic patients 19% and 11% respectively.

Urea lowering effect of dietary fibers including acacia gum

However, The use of locust bean gum and ispaghula were not considered to have practical value for clinical use because of the development of side effects.

Urea lowering effect of dietary fibers including acacia gum

The use of locust bean gum was associated with two to three soft voluminous stools daily that had an unusual bad smell ,and more importantly, the low palatability was considered a serious disadvantage. Similarly patients ingested ispaghula found it unpalatable, felt unwell, or had diarrhea.

Urea lowering effect of dietary fibers including acacia gum

In 1996, Tetens et al showed in an experimental study on rats that dietary fiber (maize bran) supplementation caused a dose dependent significant increase in fecal nitrogen excretion in association with reduction in nitrogen retention.

Urea lowering effect of dietary fibers including acacia gum

The shift in nitrogen excretion from urine to feces was explained largely by the degree of microbial fermentation in the large intestine caused by dietary fiber that have modifying role on the enterohepatic cycle of nitrogen.

Urea lowering effect of acacia gum and dietary fibers

In 1996, Bliss et al reported a study included 16 adult patients with asymptomatic chronic renal failure on low protein diet, they were randomly assigned to receive acacia gum (50 g daily) or oral placebo (1 g daily).

Urea lowering effect of acacia gum and dietary fibers

Acacia gum supplementation was associated with lower serum urea, and the patients had greater fecal masses and greater fecal nitrogen excretion in comparison with period they were on low protein diet alone and in comparison with control patients on pectin supplementation instead of acacia.

Urea lowering effect of dietary fibers and acacia gum

In contrast to locust bean gum and ispaghula, patients ingesting acacia gum found it palatable and the clinical use of acacia gum was considered applicable.

Intestinal Dialysis

In the commonest form of intestinal dialysis, the patient consumes a relatively large amount of soluble fiber “acacia gum” which is digested by colonic flora, and cause a shift of urinary excretion to intestinal excretion by modifying the enterhepatic urea cycle and increasing the amount of nitrogen eliminated as fecal waste.

Intestinal Dialysis Components

Intestinal dialysis has two main components; a urea lowering agent , acacia gum and a dietary maneuver. In addition, many of the pharmacologic therapies used in the conservative management of chronic renal failure, many of them are also used during management with chronic hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis, are also required in intestinal dialysis.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Early during the 2000s, children with chronic renal failure in Baghdad and Iraq were mostly treated with intermittent peritoneal dialysis using temporary peritoneal catheters, and treatment was associated with a significant and an acceptable risk of morbidity and mortality, and many parents were taking their children to die at home without subjecting them to dialysis.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

During these years, I was left with no choice other than trying something new to improve the management of children with chronic renal failure.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Despite the significant lowering of urea levels associated with intestinal dialysis, the process of urea lowering is slow and its effectiveness remains much less than the traditional dialysis especially in the more advanced stages of chronic renal failure .

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Therefore, the combined use of intestinal dialysis with intermittent peritoneal dialysis was the first reported use of intestinal dialysis in symptomatic uremia.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Early during the 2000s, I started adopting the practices of evidence-based medicine to deal with the therapeutic challenges and improve patients' care, and I developed the strategy of intestinal dialysis accordingly.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

**I tried to share my early experiences in the
practice of evidence-based medicine with
world scientific leaders in the fields of
pediatrics and nephrology**

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Therefore, I wrote to
Ira Greifer , a pioneer
of pediatric nephrology
who was the secretary
general of the International
Association of Pediatric Nephrology during
that time.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

It was not long time when I received a reply from Ira Griefer. He wrote “ I was very pleased to receive your letter and know that you are working very hard to bring the benefit of modern knowledge, techniques and treatment to children in your country with Kidney and Urologic problems.

INTERNATIONAL PEDIATRIC NEPHROLOGY ASSOCIATION

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Dear Dr. :

I was very pleased to receive your letter and know that you are working very hard to bring the benefit of modern knowledge, techniques and treatment to children in your country with Kidney and Urologic problems.

As you stated, it is most difficult to treat children exactly the way one wishes in many countries of the world because of lack of national resources, and I was glad to learn how hard you work at bringing this possibility to all the children.

I was most fascinated by your use of gum Arabic in children with chronic renal failure, in an attempt to promote a low protein diet. With this experience and your general experience with acute glomerular nephritis in Iraqi children, should be considered for publication in our Journal "**Pediatric Nephrology**", if it was presented for review to our editors.

Attached is an application for membership in the **International Pediatric Nephrology Association**, and also for a subscription to the Journal "**Pediatric Nephrology**", which is published 12 times a year.

I would be interested to know if there is a Pediatric Nephrology Club or working group in your country, and could you possibly be in touch with those colleagues who are considered Pediatric Nephrologists in your country, so as to make them members of this International Society, receive the Journal and be up-to-date on the latest approaches to the problems in Kidney and Urologic Disease of children and adolescents.

Dr. Jawad
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I would be most supportive of helping you become members, by subsidizing the membership of you and your colleagues for a short period of time.

Also, I am looking forward to the continuing development of the **Pan Arab Pediatric Nephrology Association (PAPNA)**, whose next meeting will take place in Riyadh in the middle of **November, 2000**.

Looking forward to hearing from you.

Sincerely,

Ira Greifer M.D.
Professor of Pediatrics & Nephrology
Montefiore Medical Center/Albert
Einstein College of Medicine

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enclosure

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Ira Greifer also wrote “ I was most fascinated by your use of gum Arabic in children with chronic renal failure, in attempt to promote low protein diet. With this experience and your general experience with acute glomerular nephritis in Iraqi children, should be considered for publication in our journal “Pediatric Nephrology”, if it was presented for review to our editors.”

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Ira Grier also sent an application for membership in the International Pediatric Nephrology Association, and I soon became a member of the international association during that time

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Thereafter, the first clinical use of intestinal dialysis in symptomatic uremia was published during May,2002, in Pediatric Nephrology”.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Al-Mosawi AJ. The challenge of chronic renal failure in the developing world: possible use of acacia gum. *Pediatr Nephrol.* 2002; 17(5):390-1. PMID: 12042902.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

In this paper, I described the use of intestinal dialysis (acacia gum supplementation and low protein diet) with intermittent peritoneal dialysis to treat a seven year old boy with an extreme form of end-stage renal disease (anuric with no renal function).

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Before referral, he was treated with peritoneal dialysis sessions intermittently whenever became symptomatic with marked nausea, tachypnea (acidotic breathing), and generalized edema from fluid overload.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

When the patient was symptomatic, blood urea usually ranged from 37.4 to 53.9 mmol/l. After each 24-72 hour peritoneal dialysis session, blood urea usually fell to below 16.6 mmol/l.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

During 108 days of anuria, he was treated with 12 sessions of intermittent peritoneal dialysis (average frequency: one session of dialysis every 9 days). When, I first saw the child, despite low-protein diet and fluid restriction, he required 12 sessions of peritoneal dialysis.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

He was receiving nifedipine 2 mg/kg daily to control hypertension. His diastolic blood pressure was reduced to 100 mmHg. He was also given frusemide for 3 days, but the effect was almost negligible. Propranolol was added at a dose of 2 mg/kg daily and lowered blood pressure to 120/80 mmHg.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Intestinal dialysis was initiated and continued for 48 days. Dietary protein was restricted to 0.5 g/kg per day given largely in the form of egg albumin. Fluid and salt were also restricted. A high-caloric diet was encouraged, together with supplementation of water-soluble vitamins, calcium, and iron.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Acacia gum powder was given at a dose of 0.5 g/kg daily in 2-3 divided doses. Acacia gum was diluted with the minimal amount of water to make it acceptable.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

The patient became symptomatic with anorexia, tachypnea (acidotic breathing), and edema 27 days after the initiation of intestinal dialysis. His blood urea was 49.8 mmol/l, and he required a dialysis session. The child became symptomatic and needed the second session of intermittent peritoneal dialysis after another 21 days.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

The child found acacia gum acceptable (palatable), but taking it was associated with one or two voluminous stools daily that had an unusual smell (similar to the smell of urine). This effect of acacia on stool did not interfere with compliance.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

A suitable dose of acacia gum powder was 0.5 g/kg daily. A trial of a higher dose of 1 g/kg per day in this patient was performed in an attempt to increase the efficiency of intestinal dialysis.

However, this increase resulted in abdominal distention and discomfort that interfered with sleep at night. The dose of acacia gum powder was reduced again to 0.5 g/kg per day.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

In this child, intestinal dialysis was associated with a beneficial antihypertensive effect. Before the initiation of intestinal dialysis, diastolic blood pressure was maintained at 80 mmHg with nifedipine and propranolol. Diastolic blood pressure was maintained at 80 mmHg with intestinal dialysis alone for 3 weeks.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Compliance with all of the components of intestinal dialysis was better during the first 27 days of therapy. After two weeks of the initiation of intestinal dialysis, it was necessary to stop antihypertensive medications (nifedipine and propranolol) because the diastolic blood pressure dropped to 45–50 mmHg for no obvious reason (such as gastrointestinal bleeding).

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Although the parents noticed the beneficial effect of intestinal dialysis, they couldn't ensure the child's compliance with treatment.

The first clinical use of Intestinal Dialysis in symptomatic uremia

Non adherence to intestinal dialysis therapeutic components led to severe hypertension (blood pressure 160/140 mmHg) and the uremic symptoms reappeared, and the child died shortly after an intermittent peritoneal dialysis session.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

In 2004, I published the second paper reporting the use of intestinal dialysis in symptomatic uremia.

Al-Mosawi AJ. Acacia gum supplementation of a low-protein diet in children with end-stage renal disease. *Pediatr Nephrol* 2004 Oct; 19 (10):1156-9.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom was achieved in two patients who had less severe disease than the first reported patient treated with this method, and they had excellent compliance with the therapy.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

Six patients with end-stage renal disease and significant uremia that required at least one dialysis session to maintain life were studied.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

Intestinal dialysis was initiated in three of six patients with the aim of improving wellbeing and reducing the need for dialysis. The other three patients were treated with intermittent peritoneal dialysis; all died within less than 6 months.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

The three patients treated with intestinal dialysis aged between 11-13 years (each with, oxalosis, cystinosis, and end-stage renal disease of undetermined etiology). They had symptomatic uremia that required at least one session of intermittent peritoneal dialysis despite low-protein diet and other conservative measures of chronic renal failure.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

They had no reductions in urine output nor edema and were normotensive. Their pre - dialysis creatinine clearance was less than 5 ml/min when calculated by a formula developed by Cock and Gault . One of the patients complied with intestinal dialysis therapy for only 10 days and died after 6 months despite treating him with intermittent peritoneal dialysis.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

Two of the three patients were treated for one year with intestinal dialysis. Both patients reported improved wellbeing. Neither became acidotic or uremic, and didn't require dialysis during the one year period of the study. Both patients maintained serum creatinine and urea levels not previously achieved without dialysis.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

Of the 2 surviving patients treated with intestinal dialysis, one patient couldn't comply with therapy and stopped most of the components of intestinal dialysis after one year and died within one month despite treatment with intermittent peritoneal dialysis.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

The other patient continued to be treated with intestinal dialysis and continued to experience improved wellbeing and dialysis freedom during 6 completed years

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

The achievement of four-year dialysis freedom in this patient was published in 2007.

Al-Mosawi AJ. The use of acacia gum in end stage renal failure. *J Trop Pediatr* 2007; 53(5):362-5. 2007 May 21. PMID: 17517814.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

The achievement of six-year dialysis freedom in this patient was published in 2009.

Al-Mosawi AJ. Six-year dialysis freedom in end-stage renal disease. Clin Exp Nephrol 2009; 13(5):494-500. PMID:19479191.

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 Japanese Society of Nephrology

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

The patient who achieved six-year dialysis freedom was an 11-year-old girl with End-renal failure who initially required four sessions of intermittent peritoneal dialysis to control uremic symptoms despite conservative measures. The parents refused further treatment by dialysis.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

Thereafter, she was treated with intestinal dialysis. During 6 years of therapy, the girl continued in experiencing improved well-being and good participation in outdoor activities. Mild uremic symptoms occurred only during periods of noncompliance.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

Periods of decreased compliance with pharmacologic therapies were associated with anemia and renal osteodystrophy and some degree of genu valgum has resulted.

Intestinal Dialysis: Long-term peritoneal dialysis freedom

The chronicity of her illness was confirmed by the presence of small contracted kidneys, a finding that has not changed during the subsequent follow-up.

Intestinal dialysis in adult patients with symptomatic uremia

In 2006, I published a research paper describing the use of intestinal dialysis in 11 patients with symptomatic uremia .

Al-Mosawi, AJ. Acacia gum therapeutic potential: possible role in the management of uremia: a new potential medicine.

Therapy 2006; 3(2) 301-321.

Intestinal dialysis in adult patients with symptomatic uremia

The patients' ages ranged from 14 to 65 years (Mean 41.45 year). Two of them were on hemodialysis. The remaining patients were on low protein diet combined with other medical treatments of chronic renal failure, including one patient has undergone one peritoneal dialysis session before referral.

Intestinal dialysis in adult patients with symptomatic uremia

The intestinal dialysis therapeutic regimen included dietary proteins restriction to 0.5 g/kg with at least 50% of the total intake given as egg albumin. Protein and phosphorus restriction was primarily achieved by restriction of meat, poultry, fish, milk, cheese, yogurt, and legumes.

Intestinal dialysis in adult patients with symptomatic uremia

Additional restriction of potassium rich foods was made during elevations of serum potassium above 5 mmol /L.

Powder acacia gum 1g/kg/day (Maximum 75 g) in 2-3 divided doses diluted with desired amounts of water.

Intestinal dialysis in adult patients with symptomatic uremia

The use of intestinal dialysis in this study was associated with amelioration of the uremic symptoms and improved general wellbeing as long as the patients were compliant with the therapeutic protocol. The patients were followed for 2-16 weeks.

Intestinal dialysis in adult patients with symptomatic uremia

However, the most significant finding in this study was the achievement of hemodialysis freedom in 2 of these patients, both of them has a vascular access, but they considered hemodialysis associated with a significant amount of discomfort and suffering, and they were not satisfied with the quality of life associated with hemodialysis.

Intestinal dialysis in adult patients with symptomatic uremia

Two patients who didn't comply with the therapeutic protocol died, one during treatment with intermittent peritoneal dialysis and one within one month after renal transplantation.

Acacia gum

Acacia gum is a complex polysaccharide obtained mostly from the dried gummy material of the stem and branches of acacia trees (Senegal family leguminosae). It is recognized as safe by the FDA. It's widely used in the production of foods such as puddings, frostings, candy, beverages, and chewing gum. It has demulcent properties and therefore, it is often added to medicines.

Acacia gum

Acacia gum is a water soluble fermentable polysaccharide resistant to gut enzymes, and thus can be described as dietary fiber. The principle fermenter bacteria able to use acacia as the only carbohydrate source are bacterioids and bifidobacterium.

The End

- Thank you for joining us today.
- I hope you are all satisfied for what you came for.

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